

Optical dispersion in waveguides based upon the Pancharatnam-Berry phase

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Abstract

A waveguide based upon the Pancharatnam-Berry phase (PBP) confines light in the absence of any refractive index gradient. As a matter of fact, light is guided when a gradient in geometric phase accumulates during propagation. This is achieved by structuring the orientation of optic axis in an anisotropic material. Here, we investigate the dispersive properties of the PBP waveguides by simulating the propagation of an ultrashort pulse via FDTD simulations.

Why are PBP Waveguides dispersive?

Geometric Phase Gradient

$$\Lambda_p = \frac{\lambda_p}{\Delta n}$$

PBP is a topological phase of light (geometric phase), which is acquired when the polarization of light evolves in propagation. Its sign depends on the helicity of the input beam.

➤ The periodic longitudinal (i.e., z) twist in the optic axis provides a resonance condition.

➤ Pulses disperse due to the steep variation in propagation constant.

Intensity Distribution of the Pulse

➤ An ultrashort pulse with different central frequency experiences varying dispersion while propagating in a PBP waveguide. Here, $\Delta t \approx 78 \text{ fs}$, $w_D = 2 \mu\text{m}$, $\Gamma_0 = 5^\circ$, $\Delta n = 0.2$.

➤ Material dispersion is neglected.

Longitudinal Profile of the Pulse

Pulse Polarization Evolution

Comparison of Pulse Dispersion

Conclusions

- The pulse propagating in a GRIN waveguide (with comparable design parameters) displays a comparatively lower dispersion.
- The PBP waveguide provides a comparatively higher dispersion due to the phase-matching condition required to achieve the necessary accumulation in geometric phase.
- The pulse dispersion in the PBP waveguides is highly tunable by varying the input wavelength.

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